

*Editorial Desk***National Organ and Tissue Transplant Organization Takes a Step Forward in the Right Direction****Sunil Shroff**

MOHAN Foundation, India

The National Organ and Tissue Transplant Organization (NOTTO), under the Directorate General of Health Services of the Ministry of Health & Family Welfare, organized a two-day event called the "Chintan Shivir" on August 30 - 31, 2024. The primary goal of this event was to bring together key stakeholders from across India involved in organ donation and transplantation, to discuss necessary reforms for improving organ and tissue donation in the country. The discussions focused on enhancing technology, streamlining processes, and revising the legislative framework governing organ transplantation.

To ensure a comprehensive review, ten working groups were formed to address different areas of the organ transplantation ecosystem. Each group consisted of 10 to 20 members, including a representative from NOTTO, and held several virtual meetings prior to the event. During the physical meeting, each group presented their findings and proposed reforms. This marked the first time such a wide-ranging, collaborative effort had been made since the inception of NOTTO (2014), providing a platform for states and stakeholders to raise concerns and propose solutions.

Key Outcome: Need for Uniform Policies

One of the most significant conclusions of the Chintan Shivir was the realization that a uniform national policy for organ donation and transplantation is essential. This would ensure that all states and the Union Territories follow the same procedures, making the program more efficient and seamless. However, the challenge is that health is a state subject in India, making national policy implementation complex. Collaboration between central and state governments was seen as crucial for the success of these reforms.

Key Problems Identified:

1. Organ retrieval and utilization inefficiencies
2. Training and capacity gaps
3. Legislative and policy gaps
4. Lack of awareness among public and medical professionals

Proposed Solutions:

1. Improving organ retrieval and allocation
2. Expanding training and capacity building
3. Policy and legislative reforms
4. **Public awareness and social mobilization**

The Chintan Shivir has laid the groundwork for a more efficient organ transplantation ecosystem in India by emphasizing the need for uniform policies, enhanced training, and increased public awareness. These reforms, once implemented, could significantly improve organ donation rates and ensure better utilization of donated organs.

Chintan Shivir is discussed in detail on page 11.

Corresponding Author: Dr. Sunil Shroff,
MOHAN Foundation, Chennai, Tamil Nadu, India
Email: shroff@mohanfoundation.org

To cite : Shroff S. National Organ and Tissue Transplant Organization Takes a Step Forward in the Right Direction. Indian Transplant Newsletter. 2024 Jul-Sep; 23(3):p1.

